

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 19/10/2015 – 23/10/2015

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Plans:

- Edit Revision 3 of the Evaluation Report
- Continue contiki troubleshooting
- Start work on WIMEA-ICT poster design
- Finish 4th and Final Assignment for MNF990 Ethics and Science course

Activities:

- All: Sections of the revision 3 of the evaluation report are being recompiled to finalize the task before end of next week. Revision 3 is being published in LaTeX, which we have decided to use to keep easily track of our references and formatting.
- All: Finished the MNF 990 compulsory course and uploaded the final assignment. The requirement was 5 pages (2500 words) of a any topic we'd covered in class.
- Byamukama: A contiki based application has finally been deployed successfully onto an RS-mote. This was a simple application to blink the LEDs. It was observed that a power on reset is necessary to get the application to run. It is possible that earlier code did not have any bugs and as this requirement had not yet been identified.
- Nsabagwa: Started an online course on Research Writing at <http://www.authoraid.info/en/news/details/952/>
- Work has started on the WIMEA poster to be presented on 12th November at the conference here: <https://sustainablebusiness.b.uib.no/> All RCs are involved.

Plans for next week

- Finish and send Revision 3 of the Bergen Evaluation Report
- Discussions and selection of 2 student groups at the Dept. of Electrical & Computer Engineering at Makerere to work with Max on power-related design for the EA prototype